

Deliverable 2.3

Recommendations for research priorities and innovation strategies

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 731599. The author is solely responsible for its content, the Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services	

COVER AND CONTROL PAGE OF DOCUMENT	
Project Acronym:	Platforms4CPS
Project Full Name:	Creating the CPS Vision, Strategy, Technology Building Blocks and Supporting Ecosystem for Future CPS Platforms
Grant Agreement No.:	731599
Programme	ICT-1: Cyber-Physical-Systems
Instrument:	Coordination & support action
Start date of project:	01.11.2016
Duration:	24 months
Deliverable No.:	D2.3
Document name:	Recommendations for research priorities and innovation strategies
Work Package	WP 2
Associated Task	Task(s) 2.5, 2.6
Nature ¹	R
Dissemination Level ²	PU
Version:	1.0
Actual Submission Date:	25-11-2018
Contractual Submission Date	31-10-2018
Editor: Institution: E-mail:	Holger Pfeifer fortiss pfeifer@fortiss.org

¹ R=Report, DEC= Websites, patents filling, etc., O=Other

² PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Change Control

Document History

Version	Date	Change History	Author(s)	Organisation(s)
0.1	05.07.2017	Initial draft for research recommendations	H. Pfeifer et al.	fortiss
0.2	11.07.2018	Agreed set of recommendations	All	All
0.3	12.07.2018	Innovation strategies	H. Thompson	THHINK
0.4	10.09.2018	Draft structure, consolidated recommendations	H. Pfeifer	fortiss
0.9	14.11.2018	Final draft for internal review	H. Pfeifer	fortiss
0.91	23.11.2018	Quality Review	C. Robinson	Thales
1.0	25.11.2018	Final version including consortium feedback	H. Pfeifer	fortiss

Distribution List

Date	Issue	Group
14.11.2018	Complete draft for consortium review	Project consortium
20.11.2018	Final version	Coordinator

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Research priorities	10
2.1 Key Research Needs	10
2.2 Coordination measures	13
3 Innovation strategies	14
3.1 Barriers to Innovation for SMEs	14
3.2 Barriers for Innovation in Large Companies.....	14
3.3 Different Strategies to Encourage Innovation.....	15
3.4 Actions Required to Specifically Accelerate Innovation and Adoption of AI.....	23
4 Key Recommendations.....	24
4.1 Short Term - Horizon 2020.....	25
4.2 Longer Term - Horizon Europe	27
4.3 Research Recommendations	28
4.4 Innovation Recommendations.....	30
5 Conclusion	32

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the Platforms4CPS recommendations regarding research and innovation. In the context of Platforms4CPS, research is considered as the creation and testing of new concepts and innovation is about bringing these ideas successfully to the market. The recommendations are the result of various activities that the Platform4CPS consortium has carried out over the project lifetime. These activities included in-depth analyses of all areas that are key to the successful uptake of CPS technology in innovative applications. This starts from the need for a better understanding of the scientific foundations of CPS Engineering, to analysing CPS domains and corresponding research roadmaps to develop consensus about specific areas where research is needed with high priority. Furthermore the project looked at existing European innovation support mechanisms and analysed the market landscapes in important CPS domains to identify opportunities and challenges in CPS for businesses.

Based on this, one of the main pillars of the project work was to devise a set of key recommendations for the European Commission for actions needed to address the fundamental scientific challenges in the main priority areas of CPS research, and to remove barriers to innovation and uptake of CPS technology towards societal-scale CPS that are safe, secure, and can be trusted. Overall, Platforms4CPS has identified recommendations in four key areas:

- Research priorities
- Supporting innovation needs
- Societal and legal issues that need addressing
- Strategic business support

Among the key needs for the future identified by Platforms4CPS is to tackle the fragmentation of efforts, both in terms of research programmes that need better alignment, and at the level of ecosystems to enhance cross-domain collaboration. There is a strong need for European coordination in order to establish a “Science for CPS”, embracing methods, formalisms, and standards from multiple disciplines in order to increase interoperability of solutions and platforms, and foster cross-fertilisation in both the application and the engineering domains. The digital capacity and capability of businesses and particularly SMEs needs to be increased through Digital Innovation Hubs, which also need to provide help to SMEs in allaying fears that are significant barriers to adoption, such as risks around cyber-security. The digital skills shortage needs to be addressed, particularly in digital engineering capabilities and encourage systematic engagement between education and industry to encourage life-long learning and re-skilling to avoid a future digital divide.

The recommendations are grouped into short-term and longer-term actions, where the shorter term needs can begin to be addressed under Horizon 2020 and existing Digitising European Industry activities, while further in the future the recommendations address Horizon Europe linking with developing ideas within the Commission such as the Edge 2030 vision.

The short term recommendations address strengthening and broadening existing activities around Digital Innovation Hubs, such as in initiatives like I4MS (Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs - FoF) and SAE (Smart Anything Everywhere - ICT), to address the strong need to engage with SMEs and support innovation and transfer of technology to SMEs. Furthermore, the adoption of European

platforms and federation between existing platforms is seen as key for European industry and for accelerating the uptake of CPS implementation. To accelerate the uptake of new platforms with the SME ecosystem it is recommended that further showcase experiments and large-scale pilots are funded to bring together key actors and critical mass. In addition, new regulatory frameworks need to be supported to provide guidance to industry and remove barriers to innovation particularly with regard to the exploitation of data, which is seen as a strong driver in the future. In particular within the CPS domain the areas of AI and autonomous systems are rapidly developing and it is expected that these will be key in the future. To support these areas there is a need for regulation to address liability issues.

In the longer term, from 2020 onwards, research and innovation activities will be supported by the new Framework Programme Horizon Europe. There are a number of emerging themes that have been identified within Platforms4CPS expert workshops, including “autonomous systems”, “Artificial Intelligence” and “trust” that were clearly highlighted as key themes for the future. Autonomous system will increasingly rely on data processing at the edge to guarantee the needed safety, latency and predictability requirements, and to address privacy and security concerns. Platforms4CPS recommends to support edge computing with funding for necessary enabling technologies such as low power processing, high performance computing and new computing techniques, such as neuromorphic computing. Concerning AI and Autonomous Systems, there is a need for understandable, accountable autonomous systems, which act ethically. In addition to a concerted action to master AI at a European level and support for AI developments in key sectors, a programme is required to encourage the business adoption of AI technologies to solve problems and deliver practical business value. Finally, in order to build trustable systems there is a need to maintain sovereignty of key value chains.

A key challenge identified by CPS experts was how to manage complexity at both the design stage and in the operation of systems to provide trustworthy systems for the future. Engineers need to deal with many heterogeneous components and also complex interactions with humans. This requires new approaches to Systems Engineering that can deal with decomposition into components to manage complexity and new or improved CPS engineering approaches. The grand challenge of developing societal-scale cognitive CPS that we can trust relies on the development of solid scientific foundation for a “Science of CPS”. The recommended way to approach this is to establish a dedicated institution with the mission to define and coordinate European efforts in science, engineering and education for CPS, akin to a “CERN for CPS”. This organisation can unite and boost CPS research and development across Europe, bringing together the leading CPS scientists and research institutions from all across Europe, employing a multi-disciplinary team of researchers and engineers, in order to drive the development of a Science for CPS. The centre would be a central anchoring point connecting with decentralised existing initiatives and infrastructures all over Europe.

Platforms4CPS has identified a number of emerging themes for the future including the need to master “autonomous systems”, exploit “Artificial Intelligence” and provide “trust” as well as maintaining sovereignty in key value chains. Overall, the needs for the future have been formulated as grand challenges, recommendations and actionable implementation, as summarised in the following tables.

Research Recommendations

Grand Challenge	Recommendation	Potential Implementation
Trustworthy CPS for Autonomous and Smart AI – Societal Scale CPS	Develop a science of design for CPS with multiple links to application domains	Create a €20M platform for trustworthy CPS with focus on lower TRL, more fundamental multi-domain research. The aim would be to define the research roadmap and implementation strategy for the Science of Design for CPS, which would then be coordinated by a CERN-like organisation
CPS Edge Computing	Support research actions on edge computing algorithms and architectures	Develop a platform for edge computing and promote this via demonstrators
Humans-in-the-Loop	Address the complex interactions between humans and systems with increasing autonomous functionality	Fund multi-disciplinary research that brings together human factors and CPS engineering
Co-engineering of CPS system attributes	Advance techniques to manage and automate traceability and trade-off optimisation between safety, security, performance and usability	Establish a research field for co-engineering. Benefits include faster certification, system integration and modification

Innovation Recommendations

Grand Challenge	Recommendation	Potential Implementation
Defragmentation / Collaboration	Link existing activities to boost communication, avoid fragmentation and silos	Support Digital Innovation Hubs, training, and coordinate via a CERN-like vehicle
Improve the uptake of Technology in CPS Industrial Processes	Build supportive approaches to migrate existing industrial engineering processes allowing swifter time to market for technologies	Joint-venture funding and incentives that support and document the evolution to ³ new technologies
CPS Engineering, Interoperability, Complexity	Foster development of European tool chains for CPS	Coordinate projects to develop CPS toolchains via the CERN-like organisation
Skills/Competence Provision EU Competitiveness	Revitalise EU Engineering education and raise the status of engineering, embracing multi-disciplinarity as well as incorporating CDIO (Conceive Design Implement Operate) approaches	Provide incentives for engineering education based on best established practices such as (CDIO)

³ Note correction in relation to a separate publication.

1 Introduction

One of the grand challenges for cyber-physical systems (CPS) is the construction of societal-scale systems that are safe and secure. Driven by huge business opportunities in the ongoing process of digitisation of our society, enormous efforts are made in research and development of CPS technologies to enable novel application in various domains like highly automated driving and smart mobility, smart production and manufacturing, smart cities and smart energy systems, or smart healthcare. Still there are numerous difficulties ahead that need to be addressed towards a vision of trustworthy cyber-physical systems that help solve key societal challenges.

Throughout the project, the Platforms4CPS consortium has carried out in-depth analyses of all areas that are key to the successful uptake of CPS technology in innovative applications, from scientific foundations of CPS to research needs and roadmaps, from European innovation support mechanisms to market landscapes in important CPS domains to opportunities and challenges in CPS for businesses. One of the main pillars of the project work was to devise a set of key recommendations for the European Commission for actions needed to address the fundamental scientific challenges in the main priority areas of CPS research, and to remove barriers to innovation and uptake of CPS technology towards societal-scale CPS that are safe, secure, and can be trusted. Overall, Platforms4CPS has identified recommendations in four key areas:

- Research priorities
- Supporting innovation needs
- Societal and legal issues that need addressing
- Strategic business support

In order to advance science and technology in CPS and to grasp the business opportunities highlighted in the sectors covered by Platforms4CPS there is a need to address these four key areas to ensure that the right technology areas are supported, there is successful transfer of new ideas to European companies via innovation mechanisms, societal concerns which are barriers to uptake of new technologies such as trust, privacy, regulation, liability, and security of employment are addressed, and that European citizens can rely on trustable systems.

Among the key needs for the future identified by Platforms4CPS is to tackle the fragmentation of efforts, both in terms of research programmes that need better alignment, and at the level of ecosystems to enhance cross-domain collaboration. European coordination is required to establish a “Science for CPS”, embracing methods, formalisms, and standards from multiple disciplines in order to increase interoperability of solutions and platforms, and foster cross-fertilisation in both the application and the engineering domains. The digital capacity and capability of businesses and particularly SMEs needs to be increased through Digital Innovation Hubs, which also need to provide help to SMEs in allaying fears that are significant barriers to adoption, such as risks around cyber-security. The digital skills shortage needs to be addressed, particularly in digital engineering capabilities and encourage systematic engagement between education and industry to encourage life-long learning and re-skilling to avoid a future digital divide. Hence there is a need to revitalise EU Engineering education, raising the status of engineering and incorporate best-practice approaches such as CDIO (Conceive Design Implement Operate) to provide T-shape (broad and deep) education.

In the shorter term these can begin to be addressed under Horizon 2020 and existing Digitising European Industry activities via engagement with and expansion of the Digital Innovation Hubs, linking PPPs to work in synergy and supporting the development of platforms and large-scale pilots in key domains such as Automotive, Agriculture, Medicine, etc. Further in the future the recommendations address Horizon Europe linking with developing ideas within the Commission such as the Edge 2030 vision.

Relation to other project activities and deliverables

This deliverable presents the Platforms4CPS recommendations regarding research and innovation. Recommendations to address societal and business challenges are described in the project reports [Consensus awareness and dialogue on societal and legal issues](#) and [New business opportunities tailored at SMEs](#), respectively.

The research recommendations have been developed based on findings of both the activity on the “Foundations of CPS engineering” within Platforms4CPS and of the extensive work by the consortium to produce a community-endorsed consensus roadmap for CPS. The work on the foundations of CPS engineering has strived to improve the understanding of the limitations of current methodologies for CPS engineering – i.e. where progress is needed, and aimed to create awareness of the corresponding needs to provide novel foundations for CPS engineering. In particular, this work has highlighted the needs for understanding and managing CPS complexity, the management of complex environments and inherent uncertainties, and challenges regarding composability of CPS, including composability across components, disciplines and aspects, with regard to humans, AI and machine learning as part of CPS, and the composability of CPS as systems of systems, with independent evolution. Detailed results of the foundations of CPS engineering activities are reported in [Collaboration on the foundations of CPS Engineering](#).

Part of the consensus roadmap work was the analysis of key research priorities highlighted across various CPS roadmaps, and the solicitation of views of highly recognised experts in the CPS domain about themes and necessary actions for future research and innovation programmes. The present report builds on the results of this road-mapping work, which has been presented in deliverable [CPS-Community Roadmap Report](#).

The innovation recommendations complement insights gained from in-depth reviews of CPS market landscapes (cf. [European ecosystem and market opportunities assessment](#)) and opportunities for European businesses (cf. second link of section), and build on analyses of the landscape of current European innovation support mechanisms and existing barriers to innovation in CPS.

2 Research priorities

Platforms4CPS has carried out extensive work to analyse current activities and trends in CPS research as well as to identify challenges and further research needs. This has been done in the context of producing a CPS Community Roadmap, which has been derived by analysing the findings of existing roadmaps and gathering the views of CPS experts in a number of consensus workshops. The aim of this is to provide a common view on future research priorities and implementation strategies targeted at catalysing progress in key CPS technology fields.

Among the research themes mentioned with high priority in roadmaps, also confirmed by the Platforms4CPS workshops, were:

- **CPS engineering** to cope with the increased complexity of cyber-physical systems
- **Trustable AI-enabled autonomous CPS** and cognitive systems
- **Humans as part of the system**
- **Interoperability** including digital platforms and reference architectures
- **Adaptability, reconfiguration and self-integration**
- **Safety, robustness, resilience, and dependability**
- **Cybersecurity, privacy, and trust**

In the following we elaborate on these key research needs and put them in broader, overarching perspective to develop a “Science of CPS”.

2.1 Key Research Needs

As outlined above, there are a number of scientific and technological challenges that need to be worked on to remove barriers that prevent uptake of CPS technologies in new applications and their market success. While the results of the road-mapping work of Platforms4CPS and the workshop with experts highlight various key areas where further research is needed, they also point to a more fundamental problem, namely that the science and technology for the rigorous engineering of CPS still lacks the maturity of established engineering and scientific disciplines. In particular, there is a lack of foundations and scalable principles for combining large and heterogeneous systems of cyber and physical systems with humans in the loop. Suitable methodologies and systems engineering processes are needed that can be applied to CPS that are cross-domain, as well as related open standards and supporting tools. The overarching goal is the development of reliable, safe, secure, and sustainable solutions. Adequate design principles and fundamentals are needed as a “Science of CPS” in order to master the engineering of such trustworthy CPS.

Significant effort needs to be devoted to the assessment of fundamental design, production, operation and life-cycle management principles, methods and associated risk assessments in CPS. This will significantly contribute to making CPS predictable, safe, resilient and secure. Models have to be developed for methods, which enable qualities on both system and outcome levels, and across value chains. A deep understanding of the basic principles and methodologies is required to build robustness and reliability into such systems and to provide guidelines and test criteria for needed open standards.

The key reason for the need of engineering for any type of system is to cope with complexity. CPS come with a dramatic increase of complexity in various ways, for instance because they integrate systems and functionality from multiple domains, including electrical, mechanical, physical engineering, computer science and communication. CPS are often forming heterogeneous systems of systems, have high demands regarding dependability, including safety, security, reliability, etc., and need to be continuously operated, maintained, and evolved.

To master the complexity of large scale heterogeneous CPS we need to be able to construct CPS that are composable from constituent systems and ensure their predictability. Here we need mathematical models to formally describe all emergent behaviours relevant for the design, orchestration, and continuous evolution of CPS. Such models need to be able to express both the state and capabilities of participating technical systems and that of humans, as well as the evolutions of such states, uncertainties, and orchestration principles. The major challenge here is that heterogeneity makes it hard to compose subsystems and to build models of the ensemble given the models of its constituent parts. Due to the immense number of components the design and operation of the ensemble needs to be organised in a hierarchical way, where the levels of abstraction play a fundamental role and their choice is part of the design process. Hence, refinement, abstraction, composition and decomposition principles need to be developed in order to allow predicting the emerging behaviour of such systems on different levels of abstraction. Moreover, statistical models for non-deterministic behaviours are needed to cope with the uncertainty of the environment. Overall, the scientific foundation needs to be defined for assembling large scale predictable and dependable CPS from constituent systems.

As cyber-security is a major concern for CPS, methods and tools are needed for assessing and ensuring resilience of CPS against failures and cyber-attacks. Again, these methods need to be compositional in order to cope with complexity and the systems-of-systems nature of CPS. However, to carry out such compositional analyses there is a need to provide architectural guidelines that must be observed in system design. One of the challenges of implementing security measures without compromising the operation of the system is that CPS very often have limited resources and hard performance constraints that must be obeyed. Modelling attacks and other hardware and software failures is an issue since by definition cyber-attacks are very hard to predict. However, guaranteeing a certain degree of security is a must to develop social-scale CPS to the market and achieve acceptance by society.

Furthermore, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a key technology for CPS to act autonomously and become “smart” systems. AI needs to be made amenable to engineering as a discipline. For example, AI technologies such as machine learning are used in a black box fashion, while at the same time it will be necessary to engineer such components in a way that they can be used as building blocks of CPS, with specified capabilities that can be verified and certified and ensure trust. Equally mandatory, to generate trust in the decisions of an autonomous system, will be that its actions can be explained and are understandable. AI relies on intensive computations based on vast amounts of data, while critical CPS applications very often have high demands in terms of real-time constraints, where the latency of remote connections to central cloud processing would not be acceptable. With the current trend to move these computations from cloud to local assets response times can be improved for

higher safety and predictability of time-critical applications. Decentralised 'Edge' processing can also address increasing concerns over privacy and security.

Humans are an integral part of a CPS: while the CPS supports them in routine tasks, humans are involved in high-level decision-making. CPS have humans also in the loop for continuous control of evolution of subsystems. Therefore, there is an overarching challenge of achieving a mutual understanding of state and intent of both humans and technical systems. This will enable CPS and humans to jointly act towards achieving overall objectives, while at the same time protecting the privacy of the user. Here there is a need to develop intuitive human-machine communication and interface design principles, drawing from cognitive and holistic system modelling. The often unpredictable behaviour of humans under unforeseen circumstances provides another challenge for modelling human interactions with a CPS.

CPS constituent systems are built to specific requirements and dedicated purposes, but typically, the overall behaviour of a CPS is created from the composition and interaction of its sub-systems. Cyber-physical systems render the physical world into smart coordinated objects by bringing remote and broadly distributed physical processes into the sphere of human and computer control. As individual spheres of control may overlap arbitrarily, there is a need for orchestrating these processes such that they jointly serve not only a single human, but can best-possibly multi-task in serving arbitrarily large groups at the same time despite uncorrelated requests and uncoordinated missions. Methods to cope with these novel forms of coordination and distributed control are needed, addressing dynamically changing overlap and competition between control functions. Scalable principles have to be developed for designing distributed hierarchical evolvable architectures capable of adapting to changing baselines, meeting orchestration requirements on various aspects such as availability, safety, security, evolvability, timeliness, performance, or recourse usage. It is key to take such cross-cutting aspects into account from the very beginning, and hence appropriate processes are needed to support safety-security co-engineering. Research is also needed for methods and design tools that address the highly dynamic nature of complex CPS, where (sub-)systems dynamically form and collaborate in larger systems, and act in uncertain contexts and environments.

Given the expected lifetime of large-scale CPS, such systems must be designed to cope with changing underlying technologies, changing regulatory settings, changing system requires, and yet provide the same high level of dependability and quality of service throughout their evolution. Consequently, methods and processes are needed for achieving such adaptability while guaranteeing the overall integrity and coherency of the system. Such methods have to support the complete design, production, operation, life-cycle management of CPS. They need to be able to describe the additional capabilities and guarantees of technology upgrades, demonstrating compliance in order to maintain system integrity. Processes and methods have to be developed for assuring that newly deployed services addressing changing requirements do not violate integrity and coherency requirements of the running operational system, as well as procedures for maintaining certification evidence of the resilience of the system against failures and cyber-attacks under such evolutions.

2.2 Coordination measures

The scientific and technological challenges that need to be solved to enable the construction of safe and secure societal-scale cyber-physical systems are massive and need enormous effort to be solved. There are already numerous actions being carried out both at European and at national level to tackle these challenges. However, the Platform4CPS consortium sees major barriers to achieving sustained impact of created results and innovations in the fragmentation of CPS research, engineering, and also skills development. Fragmentation occurs at the level of individual research programmes with limited alignment, and at the level of eco-systems where fragmentation limits cross-domain collaboration. This leads to sub-optimal funding efficiency due to overlaps, and, respectively, to a lack of interoperability of platforms and engineering tools, shared standards, and hence barriers in creating cross-domain solutions, which are needed to realise societal-scale CPS such as in Smart Cities, Smart and Integrated Transport, or Smart Energy Systems.

To counter the fragmentation challenge the consortium sees the need for better coordination among activities and advocates the creation of a centralised institution with the mission to define and coordinate European efforts in science, engineering and education for CPS. Inspired by the success of CERN, the European Organisation for Nuclear Research, its high reputation and public recognition, we envisage a similar CERN-like organisation to unite and boost CPS research and development across Europe. Just as in nuclear physics, where the necessary investments in research infrastructure could not be financed and utilised effectively by one nation alone, the scale of future CPS exceeds the boundaries of scientific domains and nations. A “CERN for CPS” would therefore bring together the leading CPS scientists and research institutions from all across Europe, employ a multi-disciplinary team of researchers and engineers, from computer science and mathematics, to engineering and physics, to biology, psychology and sociology, in order to drive the development of a Science for CPS. The centre would be a unifying contact point for the CPS research community toward its counterparts from other countries, and an anchoring point connecting with currently decentralised existing initiatives and infrastructures all over Europe.

Such an organisation would need to be equipped with sufficient resources to engage in the necessary coordination efforts, to establish and fund research programmes and execute projects, to maintain the created community platforms and toolchains, and to fund innovation support activities for SMEs, based on the technologies, tools and platforms developed. Regarding science, in-line with the Platforms4CPS research recommendations, the centre should address foundational scientific challenges of CPS and define a European vision of a ‘Science of CPS’, setup the necessary research roadmap and work programmes, and steer the execution of corresponding collaborative research projects. A number of these projects would focus on the development of required engineering tool chains by contributing trustworthy and secure building blocks to the community under an open-source regime. The “CERN for CPS” should promote building such an engineering platform and interoperable tools, and set the direction of these developments towards a European reference platform in alignment with related roadmaps and identified research and innovation priorities. Such a centre would also need to contribute to skills development and coordinate the development of courses covering the needs of CPS within a multi-disciplinary framework independent of the ‘school of thought’. In particular, dedicated trainings specifically targeting SME needs should be developed.

3 Innovation strategies

For a product or service to be counted as innovative, it must be unique and compelling to the consumer, create a competitive advantage, sit on a migration path that can yield further innovations, and provide consumers with more value than other offerings on the market.

3.1 Barriers to Innovation for SMEs

Innovation requires investment in process design, investment in physical assets, software, and technology integration. A key issue is that SMEs are risk averse and often they see investment in innovation as a risk that might greatly affect their financial performance. There is thus a need to encourage behavioural change and this needs to be done via incentives either via direct funding, providing easier access and training in new technologies or via tax incentives to encourage uptake of new technologies. Notable SMEs are very busy with day to day issues and are quite often unaware that funding is available to de-risk their investment in innovation.

Most interaction with SMEs is at the local level. Around Europe there are many localised schemes of varying quality for providing advisory information, targeting employment, and funding for innovation. Quite often there are a confusing number of initiatives (a study in the UK found that there were 133 different schemes addressing SMEs in one region, Cheshire). Specialised technical and market knowledge is costly and, as a result, not all businesses have the basis for making informed technology investment decisions. There is no recognised independent source of advice about what solutions are available and which are appropriate to adopt. Many SMEs also have a low absorptive capacity to update production processes and undertake the development of new products.

Fundamentally, many SMEs do not have the time, capacity or funds to partner with universities or research and technology organisations. Access to state-of-the-art research, engineering expertise, and equipment is not readily available and companies also face a skills shortage, particularly in digital engineering capability to understand new technologies particularly when the technologies originate in other sectors. SMEs also tend to be characterised by a high level of legacy infrastructure due to a low level of investment in capital equipment, new technologies and process improvements. The adoption of new technologies also leads to concerns over data breaches, cybersecurity and loss of IP through data sharing.

3.2 Barriers for Innovation in Large Companies

ICT has had a big impact on large companies and over the past couple of decades, virtually every company has comprehensively overhauled its operating model for efficiency and speed. In some respects driving innovation in larger companies is easier as a proportion of budget can be allocated to innovation activities, however, this needs to be supported with a culture of innovation within the organisation. This requires leadership at the CEO level with a forward-thinking view and the ability to drive change. Underlying this there needs to be a culture where employees can use their innovative thinking. Often this is not the case due to micromanagement. Management therefore needs to foster a creative and open environment that can create value generating ideas. It should also not be afraid

of creating unsuccessful ideas. This needs to be supported with good teams of people who can work on ideas and develop them.

- Providing time and money to pursue innovation.
- Hiring and promoting and recognising people who are creative.
- Creating opportunities for blue-sky thinking.
- Supporting unconventional ideas.
- Eliminating bureaucratic impediments to innovation.

Recognition of ideas is important and so there is a need to reward people for ideas. Employees quite often have ideas but do not want to jeopardise their career if there is potential for failure. Mistakes and failures are to be expected and should be tolerated. The management structures of innovative companies tend to be flat, enabling opportunities for open communication and encouraging confidence. Within large companies mental models tend to converge over time due access to the same information, conferences and internal/external experts. Employees thus need to be taught to think like innovators. Whirlpool Corporation, for instance, trained more than 15,000 of its employees to be business innovators.

Innovators, need to think different and not follow ingrained “laws and beliefs”. There is a need to track trends ahead of competitors and identify ways of challenging traditional business models. Asking what a customer wants does not often bring a new idea, however, learning about frustrations, time wastage, and unneeded complexity may lead to insights about how things could be done better. Notably, in many cases larger companies are not exploiting the creativity and agility of small, research-intensive manufacturers which could be a source of innovation.

3.3 Different Strategies to Encourage Innovation

Innovation is a highly collaborative activity. It flourishes in clusters and through networks. Evidence shows that innovation drives productivity and that interventions work best where they support existing strengths and collaborations. There is a need to support both large industry and also SMEs which are the powerhouse of manufacturing in Europe.

Innovation is led by industry exploiting research that is performed both within industry and also within academia. A problem is that there is currently a “valley of death” between academic research at TRL 1-3 and industry which tends to develop from TRL 6 onwards. There is need for strategic funding to traverse this “valley of death” via funding of an “innovation pipeline” between new research outcomes and new products and processes. This requires direct financial incentives for companies (e.g. tax relief for innovation activities) but also specific activities for research and knowledge transfer, education and training, entrepreneurship and growth. Europe is particularly strong in the ICT, Automotive and Aerospace markets and support is required for these vertical markets to maintain their position against global competition. There is also a need for action to address horizontal issues such as security and privacy.

A problem within Europe is that there are a number of very good national and regional initiatives but these are fragmented and disconnected at a European level. There is a need to create ecosystems of

interrelated networks of companies and knowledge institutions across Europe and make it easier for individuals, businesses and the public sector to innovate alone, or in partnership, with the aim of strengthening innovative capability and encouraging greater investment in innovation in Europe as a whole.

Digital Innovation Hubs

One approach adopted within the European Union to address these issues is the creation of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The overall objective of this initiative is to ensure that any industry in Europe – whether big or small, wherever situated, and in whichever sector – can fully benefit from digital innovations to upgrade its products, improve its processes and adapt its business models for the digital age. These Hubs:

- Enable the leveraging of assets by wider industry (including SMEs),
- Increase the emphasis on commercialisation,
- Widen the scope of development programmes to address complex industry problems necessitating the integration of digital technologies,
- Build a broader innovation architecture,
- Form networks across industry sectors, academia and research organisations,
- Increase the spin out of start-ups,

The Digital Innovation Hubs bring all these actors together within a particular region and develop a coherent and coordinated set of services to help companies (especially small companies or enterprises from low-tech sectors) that have difficulties with their digitalisation. They ‘speak the language’ of SME businesses, understand their needs and bridge the cultural gap between them and innovators. They offer a one-stop shop that is more than just technology focused. They provide a holistic view of digitalisation as a company-wide transformation process which enables companies not just to identify technical solutions but to finance and nurture innovations to a level that may actually be implemented – and contribute to improved competitiveness.

Competence Centres – Competence Centres driven by industry agendas should be used to encourage interaction between researchers, industry, and the public sector, in research topics that promote economic growth. They should enable research which might not otherwise take place, and facilitate interaction with industry that produces tangible economic benefits. Companies can also be exposed to and benefit from longer term, strategic research which would be too costly for them to support individually. Finally, Centres should provide an environment where companies can come together in a non-competitive manner to develop new business relationships and to learn from one another in an effective way.

I4MS and Competence Centres

Figure 1. I4MS

The European Commission identified the need to connect at a regional level with smaller companies. In support of this the I4MS initiative (ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs) was launched in 2013 (See Figure 1) with a budget of €77 million. The aim of the initiative is to help SMEs and mid-caps in the manufacturing sector by providing access to competences that can help in assessing, planning and mastering digital transformation and in providing access to innovation networks and best practice examples. Financial support is also directly provided for digital transformation. Underlying this is the idea to foster collaboration across manufacturing value chains through the help of the competence centres and innovation hubs (HPC centres, universities, application oriented research organisations) across Europe. Short duration experiments are funded to transfer know-how and technology from the innovation hubs to SMEs and mid-caps bridging the competence gap and providing financial means to adopt leading edge technology that can be used to bring innovative new products and services to market. Here cross-border experiments are particularly supported with an intention to broaden the field of the application and open up new markets. Participating competence centres benefit as they extend their research oriented activities with industrial projects.

SmartAnythingEverywhere

Figure2. Smart Anything Everywhere

Similarly the European Commission has supported the Smart Anything Everywhere initiative (See Figure 2). The aim of this is to build ecosystems based on collaboration between researchers, large industries and SMEs with the aim to transfer knowledge and resources available to a much wider group of companies. A network of competence centres has been set up at research technology organisations (RTOs) or technology transfer-oriented university institutes who cluster technical and application knowledge that supports innovation. The aim is to transfer knowledge and resources on smart technologies to a much wider group of companies. SMEs who often have great ideas but lack resources, and middle size companies can experiment with new technologies, try them out in their processes and work together with the suppliers of the technology to adapt it to their specific needs. The aim is to help companies innovate their products and services and become more competitive in the global market. €25 million of funding is being used to support around 100 experiments with the aim of involving more than 200 SMEs and midcaps in the field of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), Internet of Things (IoT) and Smart Systems Integration (SSI). Open calls are made from 4 different initiatives within SAE.

Regional Initiatives – Regional initiatives allow greater direct engagement with SMEs. This is particularly important in some European countries, e.g. Italy (Regione Piemonte), where manufacturing is organised regionally. Here a bottom up approach should be used to bring all market participants together to improve competitiveness both locally and internationally, help with qualification, upgrading and diversification, test solutions, and carry out early implementations.

National Initiatives – National initiatives, e.g. Industrie 4.0 in Germany and the Catapult Centres in the UK, are being used very effectively to develop a technological lead and provide a strategic vision of the future. These well-funded public initiatives engage with larger companies accelerating research and technology in areas that are considered to be nationally important. Here there is an opportunity to use European Union funding to provide linkage between these national initiatives to create a European Critical Mass.

Clusters – Innovation Clusters are at the heart of many innovation policies within Europe. Clusters bring together industry and researchers to address specific topics or markets with the aim of creating critical mass in technological areas. Notably clusters form a concentration of interconnected companies that may well both compete and collaborate. Here there is a need to support development of European-wide clusters and also linkage of existing clusters to further produce critical mass.

This idea is already being pursued by the European Commission in a number of areas. The CPS Cluster of projects brings together 11 EC funded Research and Innovation Actions, 4 Innovation Actions and 4 Coordination and Support Actions under H2020 to provide coverage across a number of areas. The Research and Innovation Actions are addressing areas such as co-simulation/modelling of all of system levels, including circuits, communication networks, firmware, operating system, system architecture and software layers with a view to providing model-based design. There are a broad range of use cases and the projects support more fundamental and longer-term research. The IOT-EPI Cluster brings together a number of projects as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. IOT-EPI Cluster

The IoT-EPI is a cluster of research and innovation projects that are working together to deliver an IoT extended into a web of platforms for connected devices and objects. The IoT platforms support smart environments, businesses, services and persons with dynamic and adaptive configuration capabilities. The goal is to overcome the fragmentation of vertically-oriented closed systems, architectures and application areas and move towards open systems and platforms that support multiple applications.

Figure 4. AIOTI

This activity is also supported by the Alliance for the Internet of Things (AIOTI) which was launched by the European Commission with key IoT players with the aim of creating a European IoT ecosystem that can promote dialogue and interaction to give the EU a lead in the technology. AIOTI became a European association based in Brussels on 22 September 2016.

Flagship Projects – In order to bring together key stakeholders, e.g. large industry and National Initiatives, substantial long-term Flagship research and development projects are needed that are strategically and scientifically defined and engage with many project partners across Europe. A very good example of this is the German Industrie 4.0 manufacturing and automation initiative. This is being supported under the German Government’s HighTech Strategy 2020 which covers health, nutrition, communication, safety, climate, energy and mobility. There are 10 forward looking projects with €200 million of funding from government. A working group identified 8 action areas: standardisation, reference architecture, mastery of complex systems, national broadband infrastructure, security, organisation and structure, vocational and further education, legal

framework and resource efficiency. The aim is to achieve a quantum leap in organisational management through the entire value chain and product life-cycles. Key technologies identified are dynamic self-organising systems, real-time availability of information, Big Data management and optimisation. This initiative, although driven at a National level in Germany, is also driving activities across Europe.

Platforms – There is a need to develop Pan-European platforms to support digitisation in Europe. Platforms promote the integration or distribution of technology and need to be interoperable, modular, and scalable with open and standardised interfaces. Critically for uptake they need to be affordable both from applications development and operation perspectives, with clear and easy understandable business cases. There are three types of platform:

- Organisational – across stakeholder groups;
- Operational – organised in working groups to agree on essential issues, e.g. system specification, reference architectures, or semantic interoperability middleware;
- Technological – tooling-centric organised around industrial suppliers who agree to open up part of their commercial products. Here support for integration hubs is needed to test pre-commercial solutions and act as an experimental marketplace for new product-service or business models.

Figure 5. Platform Building

To be successful there is a need to mobilise interest and commitment by large companies to work together and develop a supporting ecosystem of SMEs and mid-caps. To support this the EC has allocated €300 million in the period 2018-2020 for Platform Building as shown in Figure 5. The key areas identified for funding are:

- Digital Manufacturing Platforms, e.g. Plug and Produce Equipment Platforms
- Agricultural Digital Integration Platforms
- Smart Hospital of the Future & Smart and Healthy Living at Home
- Internet of Things for Energy : Smart Homes and Grids

- 5G for Connected and Automated Driving
- The Construction Sector is also being considered if funding can be found

The expectation is that there will be synergies with other activities under the ECSEL PPP, e.g. Lighthouse Projects on Industrie4.E and Mobility4.E. Each project will be large (around €15 million) to encourage European actors to join together to create strategic initiatives. The projects will pilot applications using existing infrastructure and be leveraged with Industrial and Member State funding.

Demonstrators and Large-Scale Pilots – Demonstrators and Large-scale Pilots are seen as essential to show potential adopters, both SMEs and large companies, that new technologies and solutions can be exploited in the real world. Here the European Union funds a range of demonstrator activities at different scales, e.g. small-scale and large-scale pilot demonstrators, Living labs, lighthouse projects and show cases to accelerate technology uptake, provide acceptance of new technologies and engage with the full value chain. Within the IoT domain the need for large-scale demonstration of technologies was identified as a key need by both industry and academia. In response the European Commission has funded a number of Internet of Things Large Scale Pilots to promote IoT take up in Europe and development of open technologies and platforms to support IoT ecosystems. The Large Scale Pilots are goal driven with the aim of using IoT approaches for real-life industrial/societal challenges. The areas include smart living environments for ageing well, smart farming and food security, wearables for smart ecosystems, reference zones in EU cities and autonomous vehicles in a connected environment. The Large-Scale Pilots involve stakeholders from both the supply and demand side and contain all the technology development, testing, integration and innovation activities for use, application and deployment of IoT. A coordination and support action has also been funded to encourage cooperation and support cross-fertilisation between pilots and use cases.

Another approach adopted successfully has been the concept of Public Private Partnerships to pool resources from Industry, Member States and the EC to tackle larger issues.

Figure 6. Overview of ECSEL Undertaking

The ECSEL-JU (Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership) programme, shown in Figure 6, was created from a merger of ARTEMIS-JU and the ENIAC-JU in June 2014. ECSEL has coverage from industry in a number of areas including micro-/nanoelectronics, embedded and Cyber-

Physical Systems and smart systems. Within the programme projects are funded in several application areas and in key enabling technologies as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. ECSEL Applications and Essential Capabilities

Call topics are agreed by participating states, associated countries and the European Commission funding Research and Innovation Actions and Innovations Actions. The total funding for these is €1956.8 million with industry providing 56% of this, the remainder being provided by the European Commission and Member States.

Entrepreneurs – Notably “the fourth industrial revolution” opens up many opportunities for entrepreneurs. An entrepreneurial culture needs to be developed in Europe comparable to that in the USA. There is a need for education via an entrepreneurship programme to eliminate the fear of failure and provide guidance and support for patenting, commercialisation of R&D results and business start-up.

Education and Skills – Holistic digital skills and training support need to be promoted at all levels, disseminating best practice and experience to re-skill and up-skill the workforce. Supporting novel industrial training methods that allow adaptability of the workforce and faster knowledge transfer need to be developed. Lifelong learning approaches are needed to continually up-skill the workforce as technology rapidly changes. An awareness is also needed at the management and engineering level of societal issues such as ethics in AI.

There is a need to develop a long-term talent strategy that identifies the skills that will be needed for the future. This may require actions to fill skills gaps, through retraining and upskilling of existing employees, with an emphasis on digital skills, as well as traditional engineering skills. Lifelong learning will need to become core priority for industry’s long-term talent strategy. As new technologies are developed and adopted within industry, the workforce will need access to continuing training and education. There will need to be a focus on cultural change to build lifelong learning into the company ethos with collaboration with educational institutions to deliver the right courses and development objectives for employees that steer them towards the right skills. Organisations face a rapidly increasing pace of innovation and will be dependent on a workforce equipped with the right skills. At a National level the curricula will need to be changed in order to create the right skills within the labour market.

3.4 Actions Required to Specifically Accelerate Innovation and Adoption of AI

It is clear that AI will have major implications on future systems and there is a need to equip European businesses with the necessary tools and skills to adopt and exploit AI-based solutions.

Adoption of AI -There is a need for a programme to encourage the business adoption of AI technologies to solve problems and deliver practical business value. In addition to adopting/developing AI solutions there is a need to provide expertise and help in building investment and business cases. A key barrier that needs to be addressed is providing help and advice with respect to security.

Skills Development - There is a need to skill the existing workforce in AI. Just training new entrants to the workforce will not be sufficient. Governments and employers need to encourage and provide continual education and training for existing employees through their careers and evaluate how to tailor existing policies and develop new approaches to achieve this.

Develop STEMS Skills - The skills needed to develop and deploy AI solutions depends upon STEM skills. There is a need to provide incentives to pursue these areas particularly at the further education level with support from industry in development of curricula.

Ethics and Trust – There needs to be a public debate on ethics and trust with involvement from government, academia and industry as well as the general public.

4 Key Recommendations

Platforms4CPS has identified recommendations in 4 key areas:

- Research priorities
- Supporting innovation needs
- Societal and legal issues that need addressing
- Strategic business support

In order to grasp the business opportunities highlighted in the sectors covered by Platforms4CPS there is a need to address these 4 key areas to ensure that:

- The right technology areas are supported
- There is successful transfer of new ideas to European companies via innovation mechanisms
- Societal concerns which are barriers to uptake of new technologies such as trust, privacy, regulation, liability, and security of employment are addressed
- European citizens can rely on trustable systems

In the shorter term these can begin to be addressed under Horizon 2020 and existing Digitising European Industry activities via engagement with and expansion of the Digital Innovation Hubs, linking PPPs to work in synergy and supporting the development of platforms and large-scale pilots in key domains such as Automotive, Agriculture, Medicine, etc. Further in the future the recommendations address Horizon Europe linking with developing ideas within the Commission such as the Edge 2030 vision.

Key needs for the future

- Increase digital capacity and capability through Digital Innovation Hubs
- Enhance multi-disciplinarity, cross-fertilisation (application domain & engineering domain)
- Foster collaboration, European coordination and de-fragmentation across Europe
- Support large-scale demonstrators in key areas, e.g. autonomous driving, etc.
- Tackle the issue of the confused landscape of business support for SMEs
- Explore CPS enabled business models and business services, facilitate access of SMEs
- Provide help to SMEs in allaying fears that are significant barriers to adoption, such as risks around cybersecurity
- Encourage the development of common standards to connect different technologies.
- Establish a “Science of Design for CPS”
- Address the skills shortage, particularly in digital engineering capabilities and encourage systematic engagement between education and industry to encourage life-long learning and re-skilling to avoid a future digital divide
- Revitalise EU Engineering education, raise the status of engineering embracing multi-disciplinarity and incorporate CDIO (Conceive Design Implement Operate) ideas to provide T-shape (broad and deep) education considering that around two-thirds of children in primary school today will work in jobs which do not even exist yet
- Ensure that European citizens can rely on European supplied trusted systems

This deliverable presents the Platforms4CPS recommendations regarding research and innovation. Recommendations to address societal and business challenges are described in the project reports [Consensus awareness and dialogue on societal and legal issues](#) and [New business opportunities tailored at SMEs](#), respectively.

4.1 Short Term - Horizon 2020

In the short term the European Commission should build upon existing activities and target actions that lead to a synchronisation of National Initiatives, PPPs (Public-Private Partnerships) and large-scale pilots. At a national level member states have already started initiatives like “Industry 4.0” in Germany, “Smart Industry” in the Netherlands, “L’industrie du Futur” in France or the “High Value Manufacturing Catapult” in the UK. Here there are already major investments in the PPPs and large-scale pilots and there is a desire to promote cross-coordination between these to address vision areas such as autonomous cars, health, etc. This is already beginning via the lighthouse projects initiated by the PPPs.

The EC has put in place actions shown under Horizon 2020 to support partnerships and platforms, the regulatory framework, Digital Innovation Hubs to engage with SMEs, and digital skills. The strategy being adopted is fully supported by the findings of Platforms4CPS. It is clear that there is a need for greater cooperation between Member States and a need to synchronise existing and emerging regional, national and EC digitisation efforts. This has a major multiplier effect for Europe.

Figure 8. Activities to Support the Digitisation of European Industry under Horizon 2020 (Source: European Commission)

Overall the Digitising European Industry strategy mobilise round €50B targeted at digitisation activities by 2020 as shown in Figure 8 with a main pillar addressing strengthening key parts of the digital value chain including PPPs, industrial platforms, large-scale pilots and testbeds. The partnership approach with industry is particularly relevant for the CPS domain which tackles key

business sectors, e.g. Automotive, Aerospace, Rail, etc. as well as key societal challenges such as health and well-being of an ageing population. The targeted budget of €3.2 billion being invested in Public Private Partnerships under Horizon 2020 i (ECSEL, Big Data, Photonics, 5G networks, Cybersecurity) and “Platforms and Pilots” (such as the connected smart factory and IoT large-scale pilots) are helping to strategically align activities across Europe.

Considering Cyber-Physical Systems, four elements of the “Digitising European Industry” initiative are of particular importance: i) creation of a pan-European network of Digital Innovation Hubs and ii) synchronisation of national initiatives, iii) support of digital platforms and standards, and finally iv) putting in place a supporting regulatory framework.

Digital Innovation Hubs. There is a strong need to engage with SMEs and support innovation and transfer of technology to SMEs. The most appropriate means for achieving this is via Digital Innovation Hubs, clusters and regional initiatives. The “Digital Innovation Hubs” are seen as an important step forward for mastering digital transformation, where companies, particularly SMEs, can gain experience and insight on novel development of cutting edge technologies and have the chance to turn these developments into opportunities for their business. The investment of 100M€ a year under Horizon 2020 in this area is welcomed and is essential in providing innovation ecosystems that enable fostering the implementation of CPS across Member States. Successful actions and initiatives like the I4MS (Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs - FoF) and SAE (Smart Anything Everywhere - ICT) should be built upon with I4MS Phase 4, Smart Anything Everywhere Phase 3 and support of Robotics as a new activity. Already the effects of this is being supplemented via national actions being pursued in 10 member states that also have DIH strategies. Notably between 2016-2017 the EC funded 600 projects in 150 DIHs engaging over 1000 SMEs and Midcaps, however, there is still a need to further broaden this and also improve the coverage of DIH’s with the implementation of 30 new DIH specifically in Eastern Europe (EU13). Overall the European Commission should foster co-ordination of national and regional initiatives to bring together all relevant constituencies from EU Member States with the aim of creating an EU-wide network of Digital Innovation Hubs.

Digital Platforms and Standards. The adoption of European platforms and federation between existing platforms is seen as key for European industry and for accelerating the uptake of CPS implementation. In this area the €300M being invested under Horizon 2020 in areas such as Digital Manufacturing, Agriculture, Smart Hospital of the Future & Smart and Healthy Living at Home, Internet of Things for Energy (Smart Homes and Grids), and 5G for Connected and Automated Driving is likely to have a major impact on key sectors of industrial importance to Europe. This should also be broadened to other areas where currently there are a lack of platforms that can be exploited by SMEs such as in the Construction Sector. The uptake of new platforms within the SME ecosystem should be encouraged by further actions via the “Digital Innovation Hubs”. Here it is recommended that further showcase experiments and large-scale pilots are funded to bring together key actors and critical mass. Strongly linked to this area is the need to harmonise and synchronise standardisation activities across Europe as a myriad of standards currently exist. Here the various field labs and pilots are seen as a very good way of testing new standards.

Supporting Regulatory Framework. The future will be strongly driven by the exploitation of data. Here there are a number of barriers and industry is looking for guidance in a number of areas. The

GDPR regulation which was introduced in March 2018 is seen as a very positive step by industry providing much needed guidance. It is also important in allaying societal fears about loss of privacy and how personal data is being used. Further actions by the European Commission in development of the Data Package which covers the free flow of non-personal data, access and reuse of data and access of private data for public purposes is also likely to open up new business opportunities. This will be further supported by the PSI directive also known as European legislation on the re-use of public sector information which is trying to make as much business data, government data and scientific data as possible available to European companies.

Within the CPS domain the areas of AI and autonomous systems are rapidly developing and it is expected that these will be key areas in the future. To support these areas there is a need for regulation to address liability issues. Currently, existing regulation in this area is being scrutinised such as that for the liability of defective products and services, as well as safety according to Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC, however, it is clear that as these fields develop there will be a need for more regulation to cover such areas as accidents in autonomous driving and to ensure the transparency of AI. Cybersecurity has also become a major concern for industry as a result of recent high-profile attacks. Certification for cybersecurity is thus a key need and this is being addressed via introduction of the European Cybersecurity Certificates Scheme. Within this generalised overall framework specific cybersecurity mechanisms will be defined for specific products. The area of security is currently a key concern for many companies engaged in development of CPS and is an area that is seen key for the future adoption.

4.2 Longer Term - Horizon Europe

In the longer term, from 2020 onwards, research and innovation activities will be supported by the new Framework Programme Horizon Europe. Ideas for this programme are currently under development and there are many consultations taking place. There is an emphasis on missions which target “moonshot” activities and it is expected that funded projects will contribute to these missions. An example of a mission related to CPS is “an integrated transport system reducing car congestion by 50% in 10 European cities by 2030”. Several other of the proposed missions also address CPS topics.

Emerging Themes - There are a number of emerging themes that have been identified within Platforms4CPS workshops. The areas of “autonomous systems”, “Artificial Intelligence” and “trust” were clearly highlighted as key themes for the future. There is a need to support this with funding for low power processing at the edge and a concerted action to master AI at a European level. In order to build trustable systems there is a need to maintain sovereignty of key value chains.

Processing at the Edge - There has been increased attention on localised intelligence at the “edge” in order to react promptly in time-critical applications. It is not possible to guarantee safety, latency and predictability for autonomous cars if there is a reliance on remote connection to the cloud, so processing needs to be performed locally. Privacy and security concerns also drive the need for processing data at the edge rather than transmitting or storing data in the cloud. Notably edge computing is more amenable for privacy/security and is also GDPR compliant. In order to provide high performance computing and new computing techniques, such as neuromorphic computing, at the edge there is a need for energy efficient computation for battery powered and energy harvesting

powered devices as well as for electric vehicles. This will require a 2-3 orders of magnitude improvement in energy consumption.

AI and Autonomous Systems - There is a need for understandable, accountable autonomous systems, which act ethically. Already there is an initiative to support an “AI-on-demand platform” with a desire to connect and strengthen AI activities across Europe. However, with the importance of AI for the future there is a need to provide even greater support for AI developments in key sectors. A positive step is that a declaration of cooperation on AI has been signed by 25 European Countries which will produce a coordinated plan for AI by the end of 2018. AI will have major implications on future systems and European businesses require the necessary tools and skills to adopt and exploit AI-based solutions. In particular, a programme is required to encourage the business adoption of AI technologies to solve problems and deliver practical business value. In addition to adopting/developing AI solutions Europe must develop expertise and provide help in building investment and business cases. Governments and employers need to encourage and provide continual education and training for existing employees throughout their careers to encourage the development of skills in AI. The skills to develop and deploy AI solutions depend upon Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) skills and so there is a need to provide incentives to pursue these areas particularly at the further education level with support from industry in the development of curricula.

Trust and acceptance - Trust is difficult to build, but in order to generate trust there is a need for a factor of 10 reduction in software bugs, a requirement for better usability, a need for resistance to cyber-attacks, and an approach to explainable AI technologies. Already complexity is a challenge, but tools will be required to improve the productivity of companies to produce dependable software automation systems, robots and AI. There also needs to be a public debate on ethics and trust with involvement from government, academia and industry as well as the general public.

Sovereignty - There is growing concern over sovereignty across key value chains, e.g. Aerospace and Automotive, as the political climate in the world is changing fast. There are two key threats. The first is that if Europe becomes reliant on foreign hardware and software in key value chains then restrictions on exporting products to other countries may prevent European trade. More seriously if systems rely on foreign made components it will not be possible to guarantee safety and security of future systems. There are increasing concerns about security issues from backdoors in the hardware which may lead to systems and infrastructure being compromised by foreign governments and terrorists. There is thus a pressing need for full European sovereignty in key applications such as defence and security, but also in critical applications such as autonomous cars and infrastructure.

4.3 Research Recommendations

A key challenge identified by CPS experts was how to manage complexity at both the design stage and in the operation of systems to provide trustworthy systems for the future. Engineers need to deal with many heterogeneous components and also complex interactions with humans. This requires new approaches to Systems Engineering that can deal with decomposition into components to manage complexity and new or improved CPS engineering approaches. The grand challenge of developing societal-scale cognitive CPS that we can trust relies on the development of solid scientific foundation for a “Science of CPS”. The recommended way to approach this is to establish a dedicated

institution with the mission to define and coordinate European efforts in science, engineering and education for CPS, akin to a “CERN for CPS” as described in Sect. 2.2 above. As a short-term action an initial project with a budget in the area of €20M should be funded to define the fundamental multi-domain research roadmap and implementation strategy for this Science of CPS, the long-term execution of which would then be coordinated by the CERN-like organisation.

Gaining a lead in “Edge Computing” was also identified as a major opportunity for Europe. Many systems are relying on cloud computing and Big Data processing at the moment, however, the ability to move processing to local assets allows systems to react promptly in time-critical applications, e.g. autonomous driving. Here the latency of remote connections to central cloud processing would not be acceptable for safety and predictability of response. This coupled with increasing concerns over privacy and security makes edge processing highly advantageous. Successful exploitation of edge computing, however, requires development and demonstration of high performance computing, energy efficient computation for battery and energy harvesting powered operation and new computing techniques such as neuromorphic computing. To advance Europe’s position in Edge Computing research actions on edge computing algorithms and architectures should be supported via development of a platform for edge computing and promotion via demonstrators.

Humans are an integral part of the system and may interact with the system in a number of ways raising fundamental questions on the degree of automation required and how CPS and humans collaborate. There is also a move from hand held devices to wearables or even implantable devices. The interaction and collaboration between CPS and humans will thus intensify with intuitive, assisting systems and humanoid robots. In future systems will have to predict and adapt to human needs, preferences and capabilities. Research and development will thus have to cross silos with respect to disciplines such as biology, computing, ethics and engineering in a variety of application domains. Hence the complex interactions between humans and systems with increasing autonomous functionality need to be addressed, and it is recommended to fund multi-disciplinary research that brings together human factors and CPS engineering, potentially also coordinated via the “CERN for CPS”.

Within CPS diverse functions are integrated to meet systems-level attributes such as safety, security, performance and usability. Above this there is a need for co-engineering to link the system attributes to manage traceability in the product lifecycle and deal with trade-offs between conflicting attributes. This is a current bottleneck particularly for trustable systems where adding new technology to the engineering process or operational CPS is costly and slow. Here automation can be used to deal with complexity management, in particular, to track the impact of system changes of a product and across its lifecycle. For instance, to alert design experts that performance or safety may be compromised by a security patch or via addition of new technology, e.g. from an SME. There are strong synergies with incremental certification and agile system engineering. To advance techniques to manage and automate traceability and trade-off optimisation between safety, security, performance and usability, a research field for co-engineering should be established in order to establish these practices and technologies that enable faster certification, system integration and modification.

Research Recommendations

Grand Challenge	Recommendation	Potential Implementation
Trustworthy CPS for Autonomous and Smart AI – Societal Scale CPS	Develop a science of design for CPS with multiple links to application domains	Create a €20M platform for trustworthy CPS with focus on lower TRL, more fundamental multi-domain research. The aim would be to define the research roadmap and implementation strategy for the Science of Design for CPS, which would then be coordinated by a CERN-like organisation
CPS Edge Computing	Support research actions on edge computing algorithms and architectures	Develop a platform for edge computing and promote this via demonstrators
Humans-in-the-Loop	Address the complex interactions between humans and systems with increasing autonomous functionality	Fund multi-disciplinary research that brings together human factors and CPS engineering
Co-engineering of CPS system attributes	Advance techniques to manage and automate traceability and trade-off optimisation between safety, security, performance and usability	Establish a research field for co-engineering. Benefits include faster certification, system integration and modification

Table 1: Key Research Recommendations

4.4 Innovation Recommendations

EU innovation initiatives such as ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs (I4MS) and Smart Anything Everywhere (SAE) provide a good starting point for addressing some of the barriers to innovation highlighted by Platforms4CPS. Digital Innovation Hubs, clusters and regional initiatives need to work together and engage with SMEs to support innovation and transfer of technology. These should be further developed and expanded to connect the many fragmented national and regional initiatives that exist. As describe above, the consortium considers the creation of a CERN-like organisation for CPS an effective approach to create strong links between competence, demonstration, and innovation centres on an EU scale as well as showcase experiments and large-scale pilots which also have a role to play in alleviating public concerns and regulatory, legal and ethical issues. This vehicle would coordinate the implementation of an overarching research agenda on design and engineering of CPS.

As well as Digital Innovation Hubs being a means to communicate important information to the right people, they also play a role in studying the technical challenges faced with adopting technology. Recent studies have indicated that productivity could be increased by up to a factor of three through the proper use of existing technology. This is a concern because if existing systems and industrial engineering processes are not suited to the uptake of new technologies, then these technologies will either not be used, or where they are used, will not produce the desired benefit. Thus, it is proposed

to study existing industrial engineering processes with migration examples to create national repositories that can be used to provide guidance for organisations to self-analyse and evolve procedures as well as tooling to help in adopting new technologies.

The industry is faced with exploding complexity and new tools will be necessary to deal with complexity and to reduce the expense of developing dependable high-quality software. Agile (open source) platforms as well as the federation of platforms will be needed that can integrate new and legacy systems. This requires the development of toolchains that can support all aspects of the development cycle from design to testing and roll-out of new systems. As systems will evolve over time there will also be a need to continually support systems as new functionality is incorporated.

A key aspect that has been highlighted is the lack of engineers and skills to support future digitalisation in Europe. To counter this there is a need to revitalise EU engineering education. This should not only provide continual education and training for existing employees, but also support the new skills that need to be developed. The role and status of engineering needs to be raised and promoted to society. Incentives are required to encourage students to pursue STEM skills with a goal of providing a multidisciplinary engineering background particularly at the further education level incorporating CDIO (Conceive Design Implement Operate) ideas with support from industry in the development of curricula.

Innovation Recommendations

Grand Challenge	Recommendation	Potential Implementation
Defragmentation / Collaboration	Link existing activities to boost communication, avoid fragmentation and silos	Support Digital Innovation Hubs, training, and coordinate via a CERN-like vehicle
Improve the uptake of Technology in CPS Industrial Processes	Build supportive approaches to migrate existing industrial engineering processes allowing swifter time to market for technologies	Joint-venture funding and incentives that support and document the evolution to new technologies
CPS Engineering, Interoperability, Complexity	Foster development of European tool chains for CPS	Coordinate projects to develop CPS toolchains via the CERN-like organisation
Skills/Competence Provision EU Competitiveness	Revitalise EU Engineering education and raise the status of engineering, embracing multi-disciplinarity as well as incorporating CDIO (Conceive Design Implement Operate) approaches	Provide incentives for engineering education based on best established practices such as (CDIO)

Table 2: Key Innovation Recommendations

5 Conclusion

The Platforms4CPS consortium has devised a set of key recommendations to address the fundamental scientific challenges in the main priority areas of CPS research, and to remove barriers to innovation and uptake of CPS technology towards societal-scale CPS that are safe, secure, and can be trusted. The research recommendations have been derived from the results of extensive work to analyse relevant CPS research roadmaps and building a community consensus on research priorities by the involvement of recognised CPS experts in a series of workshops. Innovation recommendations are based on in-depth reviews of CPS market landscapes and opportunities for European businesses, complemented by analyses of the landscape of current European innovation support mechanisms and existing barriers to innovation in CPS.

The main need recognised by Platforms4CPS is to address the fragmentation of research and activities and innovation ecosystems and resulting lack of interoperability of platforms and tools. The central element to counter this is the development of a dedicated programme for a multi-disciplinary “Science of CPS” and establishing a coordination body in a CERN-like fashion to unite European scientist and research activities, define and execute the research agenda, and enable the development of a European engineering platform. This is complemented by recommendations for accelerated innovation to improve the uptake of technology in CPS industrial processes by building supportive approaches to migrate existing industrial engineering processes, and intensified skills and competence provisioning by providing incentives for engineering education and thus revitalise EU engineering education, embracing multi-disciplinary.

Recommended actions are envisaged both for the shorter term under Horizon 2020, e.g. via existing Digitising European Industry activities via engagement with and expansion of the Digital Innovation Hubs, and for further in the future, addressing Horizon Europe linking with developing ideas within the Commission such as the Edge 2030 vision.